

PEDRI Roundtable on Equity, Diversity and Inclusion in Data Research and Statistics

Summary Report

24 September 2025

Executive Summary

On 24 September 2025, the Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative (PEDRI) convened an online roundtable to explore how equity, diversity and inclusion (EDI) can be strengthened across public involvement and engagement (PIE) in data research and statistics.

The discussion brought together data researchers, engagement practitioners, inclusion experts and public partners to share learning, identify challenges and consider how PEDRI and its partners can take forward meaningful action.

Participants highlighted both opportunities and ongoing challenges in embedding EDI within the data and statistics ecosystem. The group identified several areas where further exploration and collaborative action would support progress:

- Build on PEDRI's [Resources Hub](#): Expand the Hub with tailored guidance and training on EDI and cultural competence for data managers, providers and researchers.
- Broaden engagement: Develop a clearer picture of who is currently underrepresented in data research and explore how to better reach and reflect diverse communities, with a focus on intersectionality.
- PEDRI to act as a convening entity: Continue to provide a collaborative space for shared learning and sector-wide discussion on EDI in data research.
- Connect researchers and communities: Explore tools or mechanisms to link researchers with existing public involvement groups and community organisations.
- Reduce burden on communities: Encourage system-level approaches to engagement to avoid repeatedly involving the same communities.
- Identify priorities: Work with partners to map organisational priorities and align collective EDI and PIE efforts across the sector.

Introduction

The Public Engagement in Data Research Initiative (PEDRI) is a sector-wide partnership that brings together organisations working with data and statistics to improve public involvement and engagement (PIE) practices.

PEDRI supports collaboration to ensure that the voices of the public are meaningfully reflected in how data is used and governed. PEDRI's work is guided by its [Good Practice Standards](#), including a dedicated standard on Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (EDI):

“Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) refers to the fair and balanced inclusion of people with different backgrounds, experiences, and identities in research projects or initiatives involving data about people and communities. This standard supports an environment where anyone, including underrepresented and underserved groups, can participate in public involvement and engagement activities and inform change.”

Embedding EDI throughout PIE activity is essential to ensure that both research and engagement are equitable, inclusive and reflective of the people whose data is used.

With this in mind, PEDRI hosted an online roundtable on 24 September 2025, bringing together data research organisations, engagement specialists, inclusion experts and members of the public to share practical learning and explore what EDI looks like in action.

Three organisations shared presentations illustrating how they are addressing EDI challenges in their work:

- [Centre for Ethnic Health Research](#) – on equality monitoring data in research
- [Health Research Authority](#) – on [improving guidance](#) to help researchers increase diversity among research participants
- [Research Data Scotland](#) – on initial findings from their review of protected characteristics data for research

What should EDI look like in public engagement in data research?

The second half of the roundtable centred on open discussions about how EDI can be meaningfully embedded within public engagement in data research and statistics.

Participants reflected on three key questions:

1. What should EDI look like in public engagement in data research?
2. Where are the biggest risks and gaps in our current systems?
3. How can PEDRI and its partners focus their collective efforts to drive change?

The discussion on the first question aimed to unpack what truly equitable and inclusive engagement should look like across the data research lifecycle. Participants explored what principles, practices and mindsets are needed to ensure that engagement is representative, accessible and grounded in lived experience. The following table summarises the key themes that emerged from these conversations.

Theme	Description
Reflecting on equity in datasets	Participants emphasised the need to reflect critically on existing datasets; asking whether they are diverse, representative and accurate, and whether public involvement informed their creation. There was also recognition of the need to improve how data is categorised and interpreted.
Involve throughout the project	PIE should be embedded throughout the entire research journey, from design and data collection to analysis and dissemination. Too often, engagement ends once data collection is complete, meaning the public rarely see or recognise themselves in the findings. Embedding PIE at every stage helps ensure that research outputs are relevant, relatable and accessible to the communities they represent.
Intersectionality	Intersectionality was identified as a vital area for further exploration. People’s identities and experiences cannot be reduced to a single demographic category, and the complexity of lived experience should be fully recognised. It is important to avoid oversimplified or aggregated interpretations of data that risk obscuring these intersecting dimensions.
Transparency and trust	Data research organisations should be open and transparent about their processes so that people can make informed decisions about sharing their data. Clear communication about why data is being collected, how it will be used, and what

	safeguards are in place is essential for building trust and confidence.
Organisational reflection	In addition to diversifying datasets, data research organisations should also focus on building diverse teams and fostering equity within their own structures and practices.

Biggest risks and gaps in current systems

The discussion on the second question aimed to explore the challenges that organisations face in making public engagement and data research more equitable and inclusive. The key gaps and barriers identified during the discussion are summarised in the table below.

Challenges	Description
Inappropriate or exclusionary PIE approaches	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traditional PIE methods used in data research and statistics, such as advisory boards and group discussions, do not always work effectively for engaging or involving sceptical or underrepresented communities. These approaches can be unintentionally exclusive, resulting in a lack of diversity among participants. Multiple organisations sometimes engage the same public members or community groups repeatedly, creating a risk of engagement fatigue. Some researchers and organisations view PIE as time-consuming or burdensome. It is important to highlight the potential harms of poorly implemented engagement compared with not engaging at all, and to set realistic and proportionate expectations for meaningful PIE.
Lack of standardisation in data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inconsistent terminology in data collection can distort findings and obscure disparities, for example through varied categorisations such as Black British, Black African or Black Caribbean. There is a need to balance the quality and comparability of data with the protection of individual identity. People should be clearly informed about why their data is being collected, how it will be used, and any limitations to that use.
Limited training and guidance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is a need for targeted training and guidance for data managers, providers and researchers on EDI and cultural competence. This should include practical support on how to assess applications and datasets through an EDI lens.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many data professionals, including methodological experts, remain unfamiliar with PIE and its value in data research and statistics. Increasing awareness and understanding of PIE is essential to improving practice across the sector.
Missing voices in PIE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement with some communities, such as LGBTQ+ groups, remains limited within data research and statistics. • EDI efforts often prioritise certain demographic areas over others, leading to uneven progress across different aspects of inclusion. • Intersectionality is frequently overlooked and should be considered alongside existing power dynamics. • Participants involved in data research are not always representative of the wider population, and while full representation may not always be possible, there is a risk that engagement becomes tokenistic or 'tick-box'. • Questions relating to gender identity are often underdeveloped, yet they are essential to ensuring that people can recognise themselves in the way data is collected and interpreted.
Limitations of current research approaches and processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a need to democratise research by making greater use of citizen-generated data and community-led research, which remain underused resources. • Researchers need a clearer understanding of existing data to avoid duplication and make better use of secondary data analysis. • Algorithmic and impact assessments are essential for transparency and accountability but are not yet routinely conducted.

Next steps: Where to focus our efforts

Building on the roundtable discussions, participants discussed the final question and identified several priorities for future PEDRI and partner activity:

- Expand the [Resources Hub](#): Continue to develop PEDRI's Resources Hub as a central, searchable platform for knowledge and guidance. The Hub should include tailored materials on EDI and cultural competence, with specific resources for data managers and data providers.

- Strengthen PEDRI’s convening role: Continue acting as a facilitator and connector by creating spaces for discussion, shared learning and collaboration across the data research and engagement community.
- Connect researchers and communities: Develop a tool or searchable database to help link data researchers with public involvement groups and community organisations. This work is already being explored within PEDRI’s Learning and Development and Resources workstream.
- Identify shared priorities: Circulate a survey to partners to map organisational priorities and potential areas for collaboration in advancing EDI and PIE.
- Broaden engagement: Create a diversity snapshot of the sector to better understand who is currently engaged and who is being missed, ensuring intersectionality is central to this work.
- Reduce burden on communities: Explore coordinated, system-level approaches to engagement to prevent repeatedly involving the same communities and reduce participation fatigue.

This roundtable marked an important step in strengthening collaboration across the data research community. By bringing together diverse voices and perspectives, it helped surface shared challenges, identify priority areas for action, and reaffirm PEDRI’s role in driving more equitable, inclusive and transparent approaches to public engagement in data research.

Participants

The roundtable brought together representatives from across the data research and engagement sector.

Organisation	Attendees
PEDRI	Doreen Tembo (Co-Chair) Samaira Khan (Co-Chair) Katie Porter Scarlett Courtney Maham Zaman
PEDRI Public Advisory Group	Maisie McKenzie
Ada Lovelace	Octavia Field Reid
Administrative Data Research UK (ADR UK)	Shayda Kashef
UK Health Data Research Alliance	Simon Jobson

Big Data for Complex Diseases Driver Programme	Amy Hodgkinson
Centre for Ethnic Health Research	Julian Harrison
Health Data Research UK (HDR UK)	Anna Woolman Clare Matysova
Health Research Authority	Jane Morrin O'Rourke
NHS England	Grace Mhora
Office for Statistics Regulation	Sofi Nickson
Research Data Scotland	Katie Oldfield Sian Robson
UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)	Steve Scott Jo O'Leary

Resources shared

Participants shared useful resources to support learning and further exploration:

- [PEDRI Webinar: Prioritising equity in public engagement in data research](#)
- [MESSAGE – Medical Science Sex & Gender Equity](#)
- [Alzheimer disease seen through the lens of sex and gender | Nature Reviews Neurology](#)
- [Algorithmic impact assessment in healthcare | Ada Lovelace Institute](#)
- [Exploring public attitudes to health data research across the UK | Health Data Research UK](#)

